

32 To address these issues, we introduce the `imageRy` R package,
33 a pedagogically oriented framework that integrates data, analytical
34 functions, and visualization within a single reproducible environment.
35 Rather than focusing solely on the implementation of standard remote-
36 sensing methods (e.g., spectral indices, classification, spatial variabil-
37 ity, and multivariate analysis), `imageRy` emphasizes the connection
38 between spatial outputs and their statistical interpretation.

39 The main contribution of the package lies in the integration of sta-
40 tistical visualization as a native analytical layer within remote-sensing
41 workflows. Functions for ridgeline plots, boxplots, and barplots en-
42 able users to move seamlessly from maps to quantitative summaries
43 of data structure, including class separability, variability, and relative
44 abundance. This dual perspective links pixel-level information to ag-
45 gregated ecological interpretations, improving both analytical clarity
46 and pedagogical effectiveness.

47 By coupling controlled in-package datasets with a unified analyti-
48 cal and visualization framework, `imageRy` reduces technical variability,
49 enhances reproducibility, and supports a structured transition from
50 introductory learning to more advanced remote-sensing applications.
51 The package is therefore positioned as a conceptual and computa-
52 tional bridge between spatial analysis and statistical interpretation in
53 ecological informatics.

54 *Keywords:* biodiversity; ecology; `imageRy`; packages; R; remote sensing;
55 satellite imagery; software.

56 1 Introduction

57 Remote sensing has become a crucial tool in various fields, including climate
58 change monitoring (Zellweger et al., 2019), disaster analysis (Van Westen,
59 2000), and biodiversity surveys (Skidmore et al., 2021). In ecology, it is
60 extremely useful for estimating a variety of ecological variables, including
61 population size temporal behavior (Koshkina et al., 2020), species commu-
62 nity diversity assessment (Rocchini et al., 2010), species distributions (Feil-
63 hauer et al., 2012; He et al., 2015; Sillero et al., 2026), and habitat changes
64 (Kerr & Ostrovsky, 2003). Indeed, remote sensing is key for mapping Es-
65 sential Biodiversity Variables (EBVs, (Reddy et al., 2021)), which will serve
66 as a basis for monitoring the progress of the post-2020 Global Biodiversity
67 Framework (see <https://geobon.org/tag/indicators/>). Hence, given the
68 societal and political relevance of remote sensing, we must enable scientists
69 and practitioners to use this technology effectively.

70 Lectures in remote sensing are now based on free images provided by dif-
71 ferent institutions like the National Aeronautics and Space Administration
72 (NASA; e.g., the Landsat program) or the European Space Agency (ESA;
73 e.g., the Copernicus program). These data have become increasingly acces-
74 sible thanks to platforms such as Google Earth Engine, enabling planetary
75 computing from the classroom (Pham-Duc et al., 2023).

76 In addition, analyzed data and related ecological stories are also available
77 to speed up image gathering and ecological storytelling about the main pro-
78 cesses driving the patterns found during data analysis: an example of this is
79 provided by the Earth Observatory (NASA, [https://earthobservatory.
80 nasa.gov/](https://earthobservatory.nasa.gov/)), which includes data and stories on different ecological processes
81 at various spatio-temporal scales.

82 In this perspective, the use of Free and Open Source Software (FOSS,
83 (Stallman, 1985; Perens, 1999), see also (Rocchini & Neteler, 2012) for its
84 application in ecology) is fundamental in providing students with the expe-
85 rience of a completely free possibility to learn remote sensing data analy-
86 sis (Rocchini et al., 2017). Furthermore, FOSS enhances both robustness
87 and reproducibility of any kind of scientific analysis, fostering interactions
88 among students and collaboration, by guaranteeing transparency and flexi-
89 bility/scalability (Rocchini et al., 2017).

90 Providing students with software code facilitates teaching, allowing them
91 to understand the different commands and functions. In turn, it ensures that
92 the use and application of the software is standardized among students, with
93 an easier capability to detect errors by the instructors. In this paper, we
94 propose the `imageRy` R package, which includes free remotely sensed data
95 and functions to handle and analyze them from an ecological perspective.

96 Several educational resources for remote sensing are currently available as
97 collections of external tutorials, web portals, or platform-specific workflows.
98 While valuable, these solutions often require learners to switch between mul-
99 tiple websites, interfaces, or software ecosystems, which can fragment the
100 learning experience and increase the technical overhead (e.g., data handling,
101 authentication, export/import steps). In addition to web-based resources,
102 R itself offers mature and powerful remote-sensing packages, most notably
103 `RStoolbox` (Muller et al., 2025), which provides an extensive framework for
104 image preprocessing, classification, and spectral analysis. Such packages are
105 widely used in research and advanced teaching contexts due to their method-
106 ological depth and analytical flexibility. However, their breadth and param-
107 eter richness can present a steep learning curve for beginners. `imageRy` does
108 not aim to replicate this comprehensive functionality; instead, it focuses on
109 providing a pedagogically streamlined interface that emphasizes conceptual
110 clarity, reproducible teaching workflows, and ecological interpretability. In

111 this sense, `imageRy` is designed as a self-contained R package that bundles
112 lightweight example imagery together with lecture-oriented functions, en-
113 abling a complete, reproducible workflow within a single environment. This
114 integration is particularly relevant in classroom settings, where reducing lo-
115 gistical complexity helps instructors focus on analytical concepts rather than
116 troubleshooting heterogeneous toolchains. At the same time, we acknowledge
117 that `imageRy` is not intended to replace advanced cloud platforms or special-
118 ized software; rather, it provides a structured entry point and a pedagogical
119 bridge toward more complex, real-world workflows.

120 One of the main aims of `imageRy` is to support remote-sensing teaching
121 through a coherent analytical environment in which spatial analysis and sta-
122 tistical interpretation are tightly connected. Rather than only accelerating
123 lecture flow, the package is designed to help students and instructors move
124 from raw remotely sensed data to ecologically meaningful representations,
125 and from maps to explicit summaries of data structure such as class separa-
126 bility, variability, and relative abundance.

127 In this sense, the development of `imageRy` is guided by three explicit
128 informatics objectives: (i) to provide a controlled and versioned coupling
129 between data and code for classroom use; (ii) to minimize technical variabil-
130 ity arising from heterogeneous data acquisition, file handling, and software
131 configurations; and (iii) to integrate statistical visualization as a native ana-
132 lytical layer within remote-sensing workflows, thereby linking spatial outputs
133 to quantitative and distributional interpretation in a single reproducible en-
134 vironment.

135 In this paper, we describe the novelties, with respect to existing R-
136 based frameworks, of the `imageRy` package, available in the GitHub repos-
137 itory <https://github.com/ducciorocchini/imageRy>. A Comprehensive
138 R Archive Network (CRAN) version is also available at [https://CRAN.](https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=imageRy)
139 [R-project.org/package=imageRy](https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=imageRy). However, the GitHub version - instal-
140 lable via the `devtools` or `remotes` packages - is used here because it provides
141 access to the most recent developments and full version control, ensuring
142 transparency and reproducibility of the workflows presented. We will focus
143 on the two main components of `imageRy`, namely the data design philosophy
144 and the statistical visualization layer. The full set of functions provided by
145 the package - including those related to data import and remote sensing im-
146 age visualization, as well as data analysis - are summarized in Tables 1 and
147 2, respectively.

Table 1: Functions for data import and remotely sensed image visualization in `imageRy`.

Category	Function	Description
Data discovery	<code>im.list()</code>	Lists the remotely sensed datasets available within the package, providing a structured overview of the internal data repository.
Data import	<code>im.import()</code>	Imports selected raster datasets as <code>SpatRaster</code> objects, enabling direct use without external data handling.
Image visualization	<code>im.plotRGB()</code>	Displays multispectral raster data as RGB composites, supporting visual interpretation of spectral information.
	<code>im.ggplot()</code>	Produces raster visualizations using <code>ggplot2</code> , enabling flexible and publication-ready graphical outputs.
	<code>im.ggplotRGB()</code>	Generates RGB composite images within the <code>ggplot2</code> framework, linking remote sensing visualization with statistical graphics.

148 2 The philosophy under the data of `imageRy`

149 The data of `imageRy` are lightweight to facilitate easy and quick lectures
 150 and encompass significant free data from various sources such as the NASA
 151 Earth Observatory (<https://earthobservatory.nasa.gov/>) and readily
 152 available Copernicus data (<https://www.copernicus.eu/>). A list of data
 153 available for the package can be extracted by the `im.list()` function, which
 154 shows the data contained in the `inst/images` folder in the GitHub version
 155 of the package. Data can then be imported by the `im.import()`.

156 A central design principle of `imageRy` is the deliberate inclusion of datasets
 157 with different levels of complexity and computational demand. Rather than

Table 2: Functions for data analysis in `imageRy`.

Category	Function	Description
Spectral indices	<code>im.dvi()</code>	Computes the Difference Vegetation Index (DVI).
	<code>im.ndvi()</code>	Computes the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI).
Image classification	<code>im.classify()</code>	Performs k-means clustering on raster data.
	<code>im.fuzzy()</code>	Applies fuzzy classification to assign probabilistic memberships.
Image variability	<code>im.kernel()</code>	Computes moving-window statistics (e.g., mean, SD, variance).
Multivariate analysis	<code>im.pca()</code>	Performs Principal Component Analysis.
Statistical visualization	<code>im.ridgeline()</code>	Generates ridgeline plots of raster distributions.
	<code>im.barplot()</code>	Summarizes class frequencies or percentages.
	<code>im.boxplot()</code>	Visualizes spectral distributions across classes.

158 providing a single type of input data, the package integrates both fully geo-
159 referenced remote sensing products (e.g., Sentinel-2 Level-2A imagery) and
160 simplified, lightweight raster datasets. This dual structure is intended to
161 support heterogeneous teaching environments, where students may have ac-
162 cess to computers with very different computational capabilities. This choice
163 addresses a fundamental trade-off between realism and accessibility. On the
164 one hand, georeferenced datasets preserve the full spatial, spectral, and ra-
165 diometric properties required for ecologically meaningful analyses, enabling
166 students to work with data that are consistent with real-world remote sens-
167 ing workflows. On the other hand, lightweight datasets reduce memory usage
168 and computational overhead, allowing the same analytical concepts to be ex-

169 plored on low-performance machines without technical barriers.

170 This design supports a progressive learning pathway. At early stages,
171 students can interact with simplified datasets to understand core concepts
172 such as spectral signatures, vegetation indices, clustering, and spatial vari-
173 ability, without being distracted by issues related to data size, file handling,
174 or computational constraints. Subsequently, the same analytical logic can
175 be transferred to fully georeferenced datasets, reinforcing the connection be-
176 tween conceptual understanding and real-world applications.

177 Importantly, all datasets included in `imageRy` are curated and version-
178 controlled within the package repository ([https://github.com/ducciorocchini/
179 imageRy/tree/main/inst/images](https://github.com/ducciorocchini/imageRy/tree/main/inst/images)), ensuring that teaching workflows re-
180 main fully reproducible across different machines and over time. Meta-
181 data and documentation are provided in a structured format ([https://
182 github.com/ducciorocchini/imageRy/tree/main/man](https://github.com/ducciorocchini/imageRy/tree/main/man)), allowing users to
183 trace data provenance, understand sensor characteristics, and interpret the
184 ecological meaning of the variables.

185 By embedding both data and documentation within the same software en-
186 vironment, `imageRy` minimizes external dependencies and reduces variability
187 in classroom execution. This approach reflects a broader informatics objec-
188 tive of tightly coupling data, code, and documentation, thereby enhancing
189 reproducibility, transparency, and consistency in remote sensing education.

190 **3 Statistical visualization as a unifying ana-** 191 **lytical layer in imageRy**

192 The analytical design of `imageRy` is structured around a coherent framework
193 that links spectral information, spatial representation, and statistical inter-
194 pretation within a unified workflow. A distinctive contribution of `imageRy`
195 lies in the explicit integration of statistical visualization as a native compo-
196 nent of remote sensing workflows. Traditional approaches in remote sensing
197 primarily emphasize spatial outputs such as maps - based on e.g., spectral
198 indices, classification, multivariate analysis, kernel based calculations, also
199 present in `imageRy` (Table 2). `imageRy` introduces a complementary analyt-
200 ical layer that focuses on the statistical structure of the data.

201 Statistical visualization functions - including `im.ridgeline()`, `im.barplot()`
202 and `im.boxplot()` - operate on the distribution of pixel values rather than
203 their spatial configuration. These functions enable the transformation of
204 raster data into aggregated representations that summarize key properties
205 such as class separability, within-class variability, and relative abundance.

206 From a methodological perspective, these representations provide essential
207 information that is not directly visible in spatial maps. For example, ridgeline
208 plots (see (Cremonini, 2024)) - by the `im.ridgeline()` function (Figure 1B)
209 - extend the user’s perspective by representing full distributions across mul-
210 tiple groups or temporal steps, enabling fine-grained comparison of spectral
211 responses. Once an image has been classified, barplots - by the `im.barplot()`
212 function (Figure 1C) - automatically summarize class frequencies or propor-
213 tions, linking pixel-level classifications to landscape-level composition. Fur-
214 thermore, boxplots - by the `im.boxplot()` function (Figure 1D) - allow the
215 comparison of spectral distributions across classes, revealing both central
216 tendencies and dispersion. In addition to conventional boxplot summaries,
217 the function overlays kernel density estimates of a continuous variable (e.g.,
218 near infrared reflectance values) across classes, enabling a more detailed as-
219 sessment of class separability in feature space. Together, such approaches
220 share a common informatics structure: raster outputs are transformed from
221 spatial objects into tabular representations, summarized according to layers
222 or classes, and then represented as statistical graphics. This shared logic is
223 summarized in Algorithm 1. From an informatics perspective, this statisti-
224 cal layer implements a transformation from high-dimensional raster data to
225 lower-dimensional statistical representations. This transformation reduces
226 data complexity while preserving key distributional properties, thereby fa-
227 cilitating comparison, interpretation, and communication of results. By ab-
228 stracting from spatial detail, statistical visualization enables users to focus
229 on underlying data structure, including variability, overlap among classes,
230 and relative dominance.

231 To our knowledge, this explicit coupling between remote sensing outputs
232 and statistical visualization is not systematically implemented in existing R-
233 based remote sensing frameworks, which are primarily oriented toward raster
234 processing and image rendering. In contrast, `imageRy` treats statistical visu-
235 alization as a first-class analytical component, enabling a seamless transition
236 between spatial and statistical domains.

237 The integration of statistical visualization within the analytical workflow
238 has important implications for both interpretation and evaluation. By pro-
239 viding distributional summaries of pixel values, these tools enable the direct
240 assessment of analytical results. For example, the separability of clusters
241 obtained through classification can be evaluated by examining the overlap
242 of their spectral distributions, while class proportions provide an immediate
243 quantitative description of landscape composition (Foody, 2002).

244 From a pedagogical perspective, this dual representation enhances inter-
245 pretability by making implicit assumptions explicit. It allows users to move
246 between spatial patterns and their statistical characterization, reducing the

247 risk of over-interpreting spatial outputs without considering underlying vari-
248 ability and uncertainty (Goodchild, 2013). From a computational standpoint,
249 statistical summaries are efficient, as they operate on aggregated represen-
250 tations rather than full spatial datasets. This contributes to the scalability
251 of the framework and supports its application in teaching environments with
252 limited computational resources.

253 Overall, the integration of statistical visualization transforms `imageRy`
254 from a collection of analytical tools into a structured framework that connects
255 spectral analysis, spatial representation, and statistical interpretation. This
256 integration represents the primary contribution of the package to ecological
257 informatics.

Figure 1: Conceptual representation of statistical visualization as a unifying analytical layer in `imageRy`. Remote-sensing workflows traditionally emphasize spatial outputs (e.g., maps derived from spectral indices, classification, or multivariate analysis). In `imageRy`, these spatial representations are complemented by statistical visualizations, including ridgeline plots, barplots, boxplots with kernel densities which summarize the distribution of pixel values and class properties. This integration enables a seamless transition from spatial patterns to quantitative interpretation, linking pixel-level information to aggregated descriptors such as class separability, variability, and relative abundance. In this example, the bands of a Sentinel-2A image of Tofane (norther Italian Alps, four bands available in `imageRy`, shown in R=4 G=8 B=3, (A)) can be represented by ridgeline plots showing their frequency distribution in a continuous space, by the function `im.ridgeline()` (B). Once the image has been classified - in this case with three clusters - barplots (C) (function `im.barplots`) and boxplots (function `im.boxplots`) with an overlaid continuous variable, e.g. B8 (D), can automatically be built. The description of the parameters for every function is available through the `.Rd` files of the `imageRy` manual (<https://github.com/ducciorocchini/imageRy/tree/main/man>) while the specific settings for the figure are available at: https://github.com/ducciorocchini/imageRy_paper/blob/main/Visualization_plot.R

Algorithm 1 Statistical visualization of raster outputs in `imageRy`

Require: Raster data R , optional classified raster C , visualization type V **Ensure:** Statistical visualization P

```
1: Check that input raster data are valid SpatRaster objects
2: if  $V = \text{im.ridgeline}()$  then
3:   Convert raster stack  $R$  into long-format table
4:   Associate each pixel value with its corresponding raster layer
5:   Estimate value distributions for each layer
6:   Build ridgeline plot of distributions across layers
7:   return plot  $P$ 
8: end if
9: if  $V = \text{im.barplot}()$  then
10:  Check that classified raster  $C$  contains a single layer
11:  Extract class labels from  $C$ 
12:  Count pixels assigned to each class
13:  if percentage output is required then
14:    Convert class counts into percentages
15:  end if
16:  Build barplot of class frequencies or percentages
17:  return plot  $P$ 
18: end if
19: if  $V = \text{im.boxplot}()$  then
20:  Check that raster  $R$  and classified raster  $C$  are valid
21:  Select target raster layer from  $R$ 
22:  Extract pixel values from the selected layer
23:  Extract corresponding class labels from  $C$ 
24:  Combine pixel values and class labels into a table
25:  Compute class-wise distributions of raster values
26:  Build boxplot, optionally including density and median summaries
27:  return plot  $P$ 
28: end if
```

258 4 Discussion

259 In this paper, we described the main strengths of the `imageRy` R pack-
260 age. The package is designed as an intentionally scoped educational tool
261 for ecological remote sensing, addressing the needs of a diverse community
262 of instructors and students, offering standardized workflows and a wealth of
263 low-maintenance imagery with various spatial and spectral resolutions that
264 support lectures with varied ecological focuses. Due to its versatility and

265 open-source framework, `imageRy` stands to improve the accessibility and ef-
266 ficacy of remote sensing education.

267 A key and unique feature of `imageRy` is its “all-in-one” design: teaching
268 datasets, import utilities, visualization tools, and core analytical functions
269 are provided within a single R package, minimizing, as stated in section 1,
270 the need to navigate across multiple external resources. This supports consis-
271 tent classroom execution and reduces variability introduced by heterogeneous
272 platforms. However, this design also implies clear limitations. First, the
273 in-package imagery is intentionally lightweight and cannot substitute large-
274 scale, frequently updated archives or computational infrastructures offered
275 by cloud platforms (e.g., planetary-scale processing). Second, `imageRy` pri-
276 oritizes transparency and pedagogical clarity over maximum performance or
277 breadth of algorithms; advanced or domain-specific methods can be accessed
278 by interfacing `imageRy` outputs with specialized R packages (as discussed
279 below). Therefore, `imageRy` should be viewed as a deliberately engineered
280 informatics intervention for ecological remote-sensing education: it enforces
281 controlled data provenance, version consistency, and standardized workflows
282 at early learning stages, while explicitly delineating its limits with respect to
283 inference-ready and large-scale analytical pipelines.

284 This intentional design choice necessarily constrains the scope of `imageRy`.
285 By embedding a limited set of curated datasets and focusing on lecture-
286 oriented workflows, the package does not aim to provide exhaustive data
287 coverage, real-time data access, or computational scalability. Instead, it de-
288 liberately trades analytical breadth and performance for reproducibility, in-
289 terpretability, and ease of use in educational contexts. As a result, `imageRy` is
290 not intended to support fully automated or computationally intensive analy-
291 ses, nor to replace dedicated remote-sensing infrastructures. Rather, its role
292 is to provide a controlled and transparent environment in which students can
293 learn core remote-sensing concepts before transitioning to more specialized,
294 data-intensive, or inference-oriented tools.

295 As a consequence, several commonly used remote-sensing tasks are ex-
296 plicitly out of scope for `imageRy`. These include large-area and long time-
297 series processing, automated ingestion of remote repositories, sensor-specific
298 atmospheric correction pipelines, advanced machine-learning workflows, and
299 inference-ready ecological modeling at regional or global scales. Such tasks
300 are more appropriately addressed by specialized platforms and packages de-
301 veloped for those purposes.

302 With the data stored in `ImageRy`, a wide range of spatio-statistical anal-
303 yses can be performed. Moreover, additional code could be implemented to
304 expand the potential of the package with more sophisticated techniques, link-
305 ing `imageRy` to other R packages devoted to specific analysis types, such as:

306 (i) the development of RS-Essential Biodiversity Variables (e.g., (Skidmore
307 et al., 2021)) through the link with the `ecochange` R package (Lara et al.,
308 2022); (ii) species distribution models (through the `sdm` (Naimi & Araújo ,
309 2016) and the `ecospat` (Di Cola et al., 2017) R packages); (iii) advanced vari-
310 ability measurements with the link to the `rasterdiv` R package (Rocchini
311 et al., 2021).

312 The strict link between `imageRy` and the `ggplot2` package (Wickham,
313 2016) increases the power of visual learning (Rocchini et al., 2017), since such
314 package is devoted to elegant graphics which enhance the appealing of the
315 proposed remote sensing analyses during lectures (e.g., Figure 1). This might
316 be further empowered linking additional functions from the advanced graph-
317 ics and image processing packages like the `magick` package (Ooms, 2021).

318 The `imageRy` package is designed specifically as an entry point for stu-
319 dents who are at the very beginning of their journey with both remote sens-
320 ing and computer science. In many ecological and environmental science
321 programs, student cohorts come with widely varying levels of prior program-
322 ming experience. This disparity often leads to unequal classroom engage-
323 ment and can slow down collective progress (Rocchini et al., 2017). By offer-
324 ing clearly structured functions and a self-contained dataset, `imageRy` helps
325 to equalize the starting conditions in the classroom, enabling all students
326 to begin exploring key remote sensing concepts without being immediately
327 overwhelmed by technical complexities such as file handling, data formats,
328 or software dependencies. Of course, understanding how computers handle
329 files, data structures, and input/output operations is a crucial part of a stu-
330 dents' learning path; however, we view these skills as best introduced after
331 students have gained some initial confidence and context. While more ad-
332 vanced environmental, geological, and geographical datasets can be accessed
333 using external packages such as `geodata` (Hijmans et al., 2024), the primary
334 aim of `imageRy` is to streamline and support early-stage learning by simpli-
335 fying lectures and avoiding the typical challenges associated with importing
336 and exporting images. Once students become comfortable with the basic
337 workflow and gain confidence, the course progressively transitions to teach-
338 ing standard R programming practices and direct use of external tools like
339 `terra`. In this way, `imageRy` functions as a pedagogical bridge that supports
340 early engagement while ultimately preparing students to work independently
341 with real-world data and more advanced analytical workflows.

342 All the documentation of `imageRy` has been written in Markdown, a
343 lightweight markup language designed to produce plain-text documents that
344 are easy to read, write, and convert into multiple output formats. By adopt-
345 ing Markdown, the package metadata and documentation rely on a standard-
346 ized and widely used format, which facilitates the development of vignettes,

347 tutorials, and additional educational material aimed at explaining how to use
348 the package ([https://github.com/ducciorocchini/imageRy/blob/main/
349 vignette/vignette.md](https://github.com/ducciorocchini/imageRy/blob/main/vignette/vignette.md)).

350 Finally, the graphs shown in this manuscript are colorblind friendly (see
351 (Rocchini et al., 2024)). In other words, all the color palettes used can be
352 seen by colorblind people based on the `viridis` R package (Garnier et al.,
353 2024). This is a crucial point also during lectures. Color blindness is the
354 result of the inability to perceive peculiar wavelengths depending on the
355 type of disease: (i) protanopia, i.e., the inability to perceive the red color
356 (560 nm); (ii) deuteranopia, i.e., the inability to recognize the green colour
357 (530 nm); (iii) tritanopia, i.e., the inability to distinguish the blue colour
358 (420 nm, (Vienot et al., 2000)). In general, maps based on rainbow color
359 palettes are meaningless for colorblind people. Several packages have been
360 devoted to solve the issue (see Rocchini et al. (2024)), focusing on a num-
361 ber of different aspects, like: (i) the simulation of colorblindness (e.g., the
362 `colorspace` (Zeileis et al., 2020), the `colorblindcheck` (Nowosad, 2019),
363 the `colorblindr` (McWhite et al., 2023) or the `colorBlindness` (Ou, 2021)
364 R packages); (ii) the development of colorblind-friendly color palettes (e.g.,
365 the `RColorBrewer` (Neuwirth, 2013), the `viridis` (Garnier et al., 2024), the
366 `cols4all` (Tennekes et al., 2023) or the `rcartocolor` (Nowosad, 2018) R
367 packages), and (iii) the creation of graphs with improved color palettes (e.g.,
368 the `cblindplot` R package (Rocchini et al., 2023)). It would be important
369 during lectures to instruct and guide attendees to produce their maps avoid-
370 ing the contrast between green and red, under a colorblind friendly framework
371 to let everyone appreciate the results coming out from remote sensing data
372 analysis.

373 5 Data and code availability

374 The `imageRy` package development version is available in GitHub at <https://github.com/ducciorocchini/imageRy>. In addition to the development
375 version of the `imageRy` package a CRAN release ([https://CRAN.R-project.
376 org/package=imageRy](https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=imageRy)) is also available. A vignette including all the func-
377 tionalities of the package is available at: [https://github.com/ducciorocchini/
378 imageRy/blob/main/vignette/vignette.md](https://github.com/ducciorocchini/imageRy/blob/main/vignette/vignette.md).

380 The whole code to reproduce the figure of this manuscript is available at:
381 [https://github.com/ducciorocchini/imageRy_paper/blob/main/Visualization_
382 plot.R](https://github.com/ducciorocchini/imageRy_paper/blob/main/Visualization_plot.R).

383 The datasets used in `imageRy` are available in the `inst/images` folder of
384 the GitHub repository of the package at: <https://github.com/ducciorocchini/>

385 imageRy. Their description is provided at: <https://github.com/ducciorocchini/>
386 [imageRy/blob/main/data_description.md](https://github.com/ducciorocchini/imageRy/blob/main/data_description.md).

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